

ONLINE OR E-CAMPUS RECRUITMENT PROCESS OF BERGER PAINTS INDIA LTD.

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Abstract :

Online or E-Campus Recruitment is the most widely accepted and most sought to be preferred mode of graduate selection from the campus in present scenarios. With ultra modern automated systems and super process excellence techniques applied in the corporate with renewed focus on quality, even people recruiting has also been structured as a online flow system for steady results. Berger Paints India has been Srinivas Institute of Management Studies's esteemed recruiter for MBA Campus through years adopting a online electronic approach model in their recruitment process. Therefore through this research analysis, we have attempted to understand their flow and know the fact to understand what it means to our students, stakeholders, the online or e-recruitment domain and whole industry.

Keywords or Index Terms : Online Campus Recruitment, E-Campus Recruitment, E-Recruitment Process Analysis, Online Personnel Selection, E-Hiring Analysis

I. Introduction :

The present day and age involves e-recruitment through intense application of technologies and social media in entire recruitment process plus HR back end or operations which also otherwise known as e-HRM. E-Recruiting industry today has reached upto a point where major players are experimenting various different ways of doing e-recruiting by conducting e-interviews as well as methodologies to bring in smoothness on to their digital hiring procedures. Organizations have realized that online recruitment will save them considerable cost and time resources. The competition is in e-recruitment domain today is how one company's e-recruitment process is different from other companies and whose process yields better results. Therefore, an attempt is made to document the case of Berger Paints Ltd to know how this company conducts its online hirings.

II. Objectives of the Study :

To educate the stakeholders of this research on the advancements presently taking place in e-recruitment domain. To determine the credibility of company's e-recruiting process thereby inturn understand its viability or fungibility from futuristic perspectives. To advance recommendations to the

company based on process analysis on any adding any new features or eliminate resource wastages taking place apparently.

III. Research Design :

Data is collected through direct interaction with (a) Company HR/Consultant, (b) experimented process as a real implementation of the company's actual program in campus for student focus group, and final student focus group interview who underwent this procedure of campus recruitment selection. Gathered Data from focus group is analyzed and interpreted through ABCD Analysis (Aithal et al. 2015) for making findings. Analysis and Interpreted information is further displayed through tabular representation for making inferences and conclusions.

IV. System or Process Identified in Berger Paints's online recruitment process at SIMS :

Participating student registers his profile online with a link provided by company's recruitment process consulting partner www.freshersworld.com for screening and CV plagiarism checking. The qualified students are motivated to refer company profile, role and management information online. Post this step, the qualified students attend a fully automatic proctored employment test in consulting partner freshersworld platform. Selected Students in the test will undergo an Group Discussion round in nearest company facility. Final Shortlisted candidates in this process will attend a video-conferencing round online with Berger Paints senior management team who make final decision on candidate selection.

V. Application of ABCD Analysis to the process :

The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of Berger Paints's online e-recruiting model are listed below :

1. Advantages :

1.1 Advantages to Company

1. Online interviews are trouble free as date/day arrangement of the interviews can be easily executed from the business office.
2. High resource mobility advantage can be reaped by the recruiter for the company.
3. Online arrangement ensures serene and conducive interview process since less labour oriented.
4. Facilitates company name branded at college campus which in turn multiplies the company popularity.

1.2 Advantages to Students

5. Students can give interviews at their own individual personal space anytime/anywhere process based on their schedule.
6. Student Profile branding at company portals is ensured which in turn will merit their professional visibility.
7. Students are relieved from pandemonium or congestion on college campuses otherwise which we would see during in any mega job-fairs or events otherwise.
8. Students can also constantly check back with company for any freelance, part-times, internships or projects available with recruiters at regular intervals without any hand holding help from faculties.

2. Benefits :

2.1 Benefits to Company

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9. Alignment of business requirements anytime anywhere to the campus interview process available for companies due to quick information sharing facilities at Portals.
 10. Online Interviews can be executed anytime/anywhere as well per business convenience.
 11. Online interviews set ups facilitate easy access and user friendly experience for overall recruitment administration.
 12. HR Dept. can easily evaluate the proceedings of interview even from their remote or offshore locations.
 13. Easy provision of resource for part-time, projects and internships can also be made by the businesses.

2.2 Benefits to Students

14. Easy alignment of practiced skills to apply on-line is possible for modern age generation at online interviews.
15. Less laborious schedule will ease stress on student physique and intellect.
16. Students can better know their employability acceptance progress by accessing online industry feedbacks at regular intervals.
17. Student's individual profile is showcased on-line universally for better career opportunities.

3. Constraints :

3.1 Constraints to Company

18. Lack of Motivation from company to fully automate recruiting process with fear of losing manual jobs is a constraint in the implementation process of e-interviews.
19. The sourcing avenues may not have the IT environment matching that of the recruiters to execute the process.
20. High expenses and costs may be involved in managing the recruitment software and applications.
21. Difficult to manually invigilate and oversee the interview proceedings.
22. Possibilities of failure of on-line process due to various technical reasons are also evident.

3.2 Constraints to Students

23. Lack of invigilator or manual supervision may leave students confused while navigating online.
24. Students tend to take the schedule light and easy as they believe they can access the process anytime anywhere.
25. Inability of the student to access internet, applications and system may lead to their innocence and ignorance on job offer status.
26. Students tend to become lethargic and lazy in absence of high pressure corporate environment.
27. Student image failure when companies drop profiles of unqualified or rejected profiles from their portals.

4. Disadvantages :

4.1 Disadvantages to Company

28. Installation and implementation of process may become rigid and tedious as recruiter needs to configure and map the IT infrastructure services to that of the college.
29. Invalidity of on-line process if the sourcing avenue does not have or support the

required IT environment of the recruiter.

- 30. Technical error and system lag can delay the entire recruitment process.
- 31. The quality of manpower obtained post the process may not be satisfactory.
- 32. Creation of negative image for recruiter if the e-recruitment process fails due to various technical and non-technical reasons.

4.2 Disadvantages to Students

- 33. Any confusion at any stage of on-line recruitment may lead to demotivation among students rendering the event ineffective.
- 34. Student Absence as well not accessing the interview modules online can again render the process ineffective affecting student career.
- 35. Rigidity and Procrastination may lead the student to lose control on administering himself at company on-line portals and thereby miss out job opportunities.
- 36. On-line interview dependence may lead to total innocence and ignorance of physical interview process existence.
- 37. Image failure will depress students at campus, if company rejects and removes their profile from company database.

Table1: Issues and Factors for Berger Paints On-line Recruitment Model using ABCD framework

Determinant Issues identified for Stakeholders Berger Paints's Online Process as per Framework				
Key Attributes	Advantages	Benefits	Constraints	Disadvantages
Online Process Schedule	Easy Implementation	Organized and Methodical	Student Casual Take	Technical Issues
Online Process Flexibility	Highly Adaptive	Trouble Free	Time Consuming	Lack of HR Intervention
Online Process Administration	Anytime/Anywhere	Self-Supervision	Student Apathy	Lack of Adoption
Online Process Usage, Relevance and Applicability	Career Conducive	Easy Alignment	Inability to comprehend the Process	Lack of Initiative

VI. Critical Constituent Elements of Berger Paints Online Process as per ABCD model

Table 2 : Advantageous Factors of online recruitment process and their critical constituent elements :

		Advantageous	
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Focus Area	Key Attributes	Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Elements
Company	Online Process Schedule	Easy Implementation	Online Approach
Student	Online Process Schedule	Highly Adaptive	Easy to execute

Table 3 : Beneficial Factors of online recruitment process and their critical constituent elements :

Focus Area	Key Attributes	Beneficial Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Elements
Company	Online Process Flexibility	Organized and Methodical	Easy Flow
Student	Online Process Flexibility	Self-Supervision	Simple to work

Table 4 : Constraining Factors of online recruitment process and their critical constituent elements :

Focus Area	Key Attributes	Constraining Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Elements
Company	Online Process Administration	Control Issues	No direct control
Student	Online Process Administration	Casual Take	Lack of Interest

Table 5 : Disadvantageous Factors of online recruitment process and their critical constituent elements :

Focus Area	Key Attributes	Disadvantageous Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Elements
Company	Online Process Usage, Relevance and Applicability	Unable to fully automate	Process Integration Shortcomings
Student	Online Process Usage, Relevance and Applicability	Lack of Initiative	Lethargy and Procrastination

VII. Findings

The critical constituent element derived from Berger Paints Online recruitment Process above as per ABCD framework bought about certain quantifiable criterions for determination on the efficiency of the model. These elements is derivative out of the various factors affecting determinant issues pertaining to the key attributes endorsed by the focus group.

VIII. Suggestions or Optimum Solutions

The proposed suggestion would be even to have the group discussion GD online through group video conferencing to make it fully automated. An appeal is also forwarded here to include a pre-placement lecture video by company HR or consulting partner to guide and motivate the placement seeking students.

IX. Conclusion

As concluding remarks, we have studied the determinant issues and various key factors affecting Berger Paints's Online campus recruitment model using ABCD analysis framework. The analysis identified numerous key affecting attributes for various determinant issues under four constructs advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages. The analysis bought out key critical constituent elements under the constructs which satisfied the objectives of stakeholders.

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